

Appendix A: Additional table

Table A.1. Lines other than those of CO isotopologues detected towards the six post-AGB sources.

Spectral lines	Freq. [GHz]	GLMP	GLMP	AFGL	HD	Hen	M1-92
		950	953	5385	187885	3-1475	
NaCl $\nu = 1, J = 17 - 16$	219.61498		X				
SO $3\Sigma, J = 6_5 - 5_4$	219.94944					X	X
Si ¹³ CC $J = 17_{2,15} - 17_{2,16} (?)$	220.598	X					
?	220.643	X					
?	220.685	X					
?	220.714	X	X				
?	220.746	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{0,10} - 9_{0,9}$	220.77369	X	X				
NaCl $J = 17 - 16$	221.26016	X	X				
?	221.297		X				
?	223.303	X					
K ³⁷ Cl $J = 30 - 29 (?)$	223.78283		X				
NaCl $J = 18 - 17$	234.25192	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{8,2} - 9_{8,1}$	234.53401	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{8,3} - 9_{8,2}$	234.53401	X	X				
SiS $\nu = 1, J = 13 - 12$	234.814		X				
SO ₂ $J = 4_{2,2} - 3_{1,3}$	235.15172					X	X
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{6,5} - 9_{6,4}$	235.71301	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{6,4} - 9_{6,3}$	235.71307	X	X				
K ³⁷ Cl $\nu = 2, J = 32 - 31 (?)$	235.766		X				
SiS $J = 13 - 12$ (incomplete profile)	235.96135	X	X			X	
SO ₂ $J = 16_{1,15} - 15_{2,14}$	236.21669					X	
HC ₃ N $J = 26 - 25$	236.51279	X	X	X			
SO ₂ $J = 12_{3,9} - 12_{2,10}$	237.06883					X	
HC ₃ N $\nu_7 = 1, J = 26 - 25, I = 1e$	237.09318	X	X				
HC ₃ N $\nu_6 = 1, J = 26 - 25, I = 1f$	237.09318	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{4,7} - 9_{4,6}$	237.15002	X	X				
SiC ₂ $J = 10_{4,7} - 9_{4,6}$	237.33131	X	X				
HC ₃ N $\nu_7 = 1, J = 26 - 25, I = 1f$	237.43205	X	X				

Appendix B: Velocity-integrated maps of the ^{13}CO , C^{17}O , and C^{18}O $J=2-1$ lines

Fig. B.1. Brightness distribution of the ^{13}CO $J=2-1$ lines integrated over the velocity interval corresponding to the full width at zero intensity of the C^{18}O $J=2-1$ lines. The contours show levels at 3, 5, 10, and 20 times the root mean square noise level of the image.

Fig. B.2. Brightness distribution of the C^{17}O $J=2-1$ lines integrated over their full width at zero intensity. The contours show levels at 3, 5, 10, and 20 times the root mean square noise level of the image.

Fig. B.3. Brightness distribution of the $C^{18}O$ $J=2-1$ lines integrated over their full width at zero intensity. The contours show levels at 3, 5, 10, and 20 times the root mean square noise level of the image.

Appendix C: Spitzer images of GLMP 950 and GLMP 953

Fig. C.1. Cut-out of Spitzer/IRAC images at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ (left) and at $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ (right) towards GLMP 950 and 2MASS J19472480+2928108.

Fig. C.2. Cut-out of Spitzer/IRAC images at 3.6 μm (left) and 4.5 μm (right) towards GLMP 953 and 2MASS J19500826+2512008.

Appendix D: Continuum image of AFGL 5385 with additional source

Fig. D.1. Continuum image of AFGL 5385 including a larger region than Fig. 4 to show the second detected source to the east.